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Abstract:

This deliverable is a report on the implementation and results of task 5.5, implemented in the SSHOC project under the responsibility of NSD/Sikt¹. The report gives an overview of the data infrastructure that was developed, its functionality and uses, concluding with recommendations for other data archives based on NSDs practical experiences.

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¹ Please note that from 1.1.2022, NSD is integrated into the new organisation [Sikt – Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research](#).

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Author List

Organisation	Name	Contact Information
Sikt	Bodil Agasøster	bodil.agasoster@sikt.no
Sikt	Gyrid Havåg Bergseth	gyrid.bergseth@sikt.no
Sikt	Benjamin Beuster	benjamin.beuster@sikt.no
Sikt	Archana Bidargaddi	archana.bidargaddi@sikt.no
Sikt	Ørnulf Risnes	Ornulf.risnes@sikt.no
Sikt	Knut Kalgraff Skjåk	knut.skjak@sikt.no
Sikt	Eirik Stavestrand	eirik.stavestrand@sikt.no

Executive Summary

The SSHOC project Deliverable D5.13 Recommendations for a FAIR compliant integrated data and metadata repository describes the implementation of the European Social Survey (ESS) pilot project to prepare cross-national survey data and metadata for the EOSC.

The report explains the various steps made to prepare and implement the new infrastructure, and the achievements reaped by the approach in terms of improved implementation of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

The new ESS data and metadata service consists of multiple data and metadata repositories to support an efficient, collaborative, version-controlled data processing workflow. The service makes use of Colectica software solutions for metadata management and Azure cloud for data storage and management. The repositories are accessed via ESS API for management and dissemination of data and metadata. The architecture allows users to query the API in a range of ways.

Increased use of controlled vocabularies and easier log in (authentication) has given simpler retrieval of data. Furthermore, the APIs allow data curators to process, document and publish data and metadata in a secure and stable environment.

Finally, practical recommendations based on the experiences of NSD/Sikt are provided. Beyond SSHOC WP5, this document is relevant to SSHOC WP3 and WP7.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
Azure / Microsoft Azure	Cloud computing service operated by Microsoft for application management via Microsoft-managed data centres.
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives European Research Infrastructure Consortium
DASISH	Digital Services Infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities
DDI /(Alliance)	The Data Documentation Initiative (Alliance)
DDI-C	The Data Documentation Initiative Codebook (metadata model)
DDI-CDI	The Data Documentation Initiative Cross-Domain Integration (metadata model)
DDI-L	The Data Documentation Initiative LifeCycle (model)
CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence
CC BY-SA 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence
CMS	Content Management System
CV	Controlled Vocabulary
Datacite	International not-for-profit organisation which aims to improve data citation
Datomic	Distributed database and implementation of Datalog
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Edugain	Interfederation service connecting identity federations around the world, simplifying access to content, services and resources for the global research and education community
ELLST	The European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS9, etc.	European Social Survey Round 9, etc.
ESS ERIC	European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EUROSTAT	Directorate-General of the European Commission responsible for statistical information to the institutions of the European Union.
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable

Feide	The national solution for secure login and data sharing in the educational and research sector in Norway
Google	Multinational technology company that specialises in Internet-related services and products
Google Crawler	Google's main web crawler, i.e., internet bot that systematically browses the World Wide Web
GraphQL	Query language for APIs and a runtime for fulfilling those queries with your existing data
ILO	International Labour Organisation
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IT	Information Technology
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupations
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
Jupyter Notebook	Server-client application that allows editing and running notebook documents via a web browser
MyESS	Internal survey management tool for the European Social Survey (ESS)
NACE	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community (Industrial Standard)
Nesstar	Software system for data publishing and online analysis
NSD	Norwegian Centre for Research Data
NUTS	Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
Open CMS	An Open Source website Content Management System
PDF	Portable Document Format
PostgreSQL	Powerful, open-source object-relational database system that uses and extends the SQL language combined with many features that safely store and scale the most complicated data workloads
Python	Programming language
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SERISS	Synergies for Europe's Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences
Sikt	Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project

Stata	Software for Statistical and Data Science
TFIR	Turning FAIR into reality
PID	Persistent Identifier
QVDB	The Question Variable Database
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
Windows	Group of several proprietary graphical operating system families marketed by Microsoft

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1. Introduction

1.1 Context

The SSHOC project aims to build a Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) as part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) with FAIR data, tools, and training in a cloud-based infrastructure. Better access to data and innovative tools and services will be provided to users, and reuse of data facilitated through Open Science and FAIR principles and practices.

Task 5.5 ESS as a service: a pilot making cross-national survey data FAIR, examines how cross-national, longitudinal survey data and metadata can be prepared and provide services for the EOSC.

From the start of 2002, the European Social Survey (ESS) has offered open and free access to all non-commercial users online. The infrastructure for curation and dissemination of data and metadata was, however, in need of major upgrading to satisfy the needs of modern users and to comply with ambitions and requirements of Open Science, the FAIR principles and the EOSC. Participation in the SSHOC has permitted ESS to develop and realise the needed upgrading of its infrastructure.

This report aims to explain choices taken as part of the development process of the new infrastructure with data and metadata repositories and APIs, and to explain lessons learned and opportunities for replication.

Taking ESS to “the cloud” as a FAIR data service is a tall order. The obstacles are, however, not necessarily the same as other social science data collections would face when performing the same task. The ESS data holdings are thoroughly documented and well harmonised, freely available online for non-profit purposes without any privileged access. The ESS Data archive at NSD/Sikt is involved throughout the ESS survey lifecycle, from planning through data collection and data management to data dissemination and post dissemination curation.

Nevertheless, on tests of the EOSC Nordic project² for FAIR data services, the ESS data holdings hitherto only scored average. Given the richness of ESS metadata, the plan for improvement was set, especially in terms of interoperability. The process of taking ESS to the cloud has been more demanding than FAIRification. The solution has been to build a stable and maintainable system of data and metadata storage, APIs and aligning services, that can withstand the test of time. The logic in the set-up allows single elements to be replaced without the need to re-do the entire system.

² <https://www.eosc-nordic.eu/> [25/01/2022]

1.2 What has been achieved in SSHOC task 5.5?

A system that modernises the ESS data/metadata infrastructure and makes it EOSC-ready has been designed and developed. The system consists of 10-15 collaborating services, wrapped in various APIs that will be stable over time, regardless of implementation details behind the API (i.e., within Sikt).

The API-based approach ensures long-term compatibility and interoperability with external services and that data/metadata is as open as possible. By hiding implementation details from the users, it is ensured that API consumers never have to know technical component details (APIs can have long term stability and consist of proper and predictable domain abstractions that may differ from internal implementation abstractions.) This allows for flexibility to replace these underlying components without disturbing the overall system and the user interface.

1.3 Structure of the document

The report starts out with a chapter on main choices, concerns, and considerations taken prior to and during the development work of task 5.5.

Chapter 3 explains the characteristics of the following components that were developed and their contributions - data repositories, APIs, controlled vocabularies and statistical standards, and versioning.

In Chapter 4, the FAIRness achieved in ESS data and metadata is explained in more detail for each of the FAIR elements, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The recommendations of the task 5.5 team of the most essential elements to consider for a data archive when implementing FAIR elements follow in part 5.

In Chapter 6, thoughts on where the development work undertaken and the FAIRification exercise has brought the ESS data archive is offered together with some ideas on possibilities for replication, and next steps ahead.

The target audiences of the deliverable are other data archives and interested data and survey managers as well as data scientists.

2. Important choices and considerations

2.1 Considerations and choices taken prior to task 5.5 implementation

When the work on task 5.5 began, ESS data was stored locally at NSD servers. All data processing was done in SAS and SPSS run against the same servers. Raw data was encrypted and stored in a secure area.

Some basic considerations with great implications for Task 5.5 choices and results have been taken into account by NSD/Sikt management and the task 5.5 team³ prior to implementation of the work:

1. Repository solution - Other available repository solutions have been considered for capacity for the ESS survey, amongst others Dataverse, however, it was found that those repositories did not cater for ESS needs, so a solution needed to be custom built for the ESS data. Some of the points that were considered for the evaluation were – a rich and extensive metadata standard that supports cardinality, versioning, relation between elements, integration between data and metadata, and possibility for customization and powerful APIs.
2. Sustainability - For a sustainable new ESS as a service solution in the cloud, an important principal decision taken early in the SSHOC task 5.5 work was that all choices made, and the solutions used must be maintainable by NSD and enable a build on in the future to ensure the sustainability of the solutions.
3. Competencies - Building on / adapting to NSD's competencies remained a core concern. This had majorly influenced the choice of technology for APIs and the decisions to use the Colectica software system⁴ for metadata repository, and the DDI Lifecycle standard.

2.1.1 Nesstar and DDI Codebook

From the start of the ESS survey, as for NSDs data management in general, Nesstar⁵, a proprietary DDI-codebook based data dissemination and visualisation tool developed by NSD, was a cornerstone of the data curation and data processing systems. ESS survey documentation was processed and stored either in a documentation database system and exported as xml included in Nesstar data dissemination or as PDFs disseminated via europeansocialsurvey.org (OpenCms website). Other study

³ All decisions have been taken by NSD/Sikt management and development teams and the task 5.5 team at NSD/Sikt - in consultation with ESS ERIC when needed.

⁴ Please refer to <https://colectica.com/> [25/01/2022]

⁵ [Nesstar](#) has reached its "gone by" date and will no longer be offered to users [25/01/2022]

level documentation such as fieldwork documents and instructions were also uploaded and stored in the CMS of the website. In addition to the dissemination of data via flat data files (SPSS, SAS, Stata), ESS data and documentation was disseminated via Nesstar.

2.1.2 DDI Lifecycle and Colectica as conceptual and technological backbone (in QVDB)

The introduction of Colectica and the DDI Lifecycle metadata standard to the ESS data holdings started in 2012 in the [Digital Services Infrastructure for Social Sciences and Humanities \(DASISH\)](#) and succeeding [Synergies for Europe's Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences \(SERISS\)](#) projects.⁶ The overall aim was to serve the ESS, and potentially other survey programmes, in their business processes of specifying, documenting, versioning and disseminating survey data. The QVDB was populated with 8 waves of ESS data including the transformation from DDI-C into DDI Lifecycle. It gives examples on how variables from different points in time or different data sets correspond to each other using the three levels structure of Conceptual Variable, Represented Variable and Variable (DDI3.2 variable harmonisation, refer to Beuster (2018)). The use of DDI Lifecycle is particularly valuable for the ESS as longitudinal data is not supported in the DDI Codebook metadata standard, but well supported in DDI Lifecycle.

2.1.3 Use of controlled vocabularies and other standards

Several standards are used in ESS data (for example ISCO88 and later ISCO08, NACE, ISO, NUTS). Further ESS specific standards were developed to ensure cross country comparability in complex measurements such as Highest level of achieved education, Religious belonging, and Marital status. The benefits and importance of using standards has thus always been acknowledged by the ESS, and the ESS data archive has strived to implement the use of standards where possible. The implementation of Colectica prior to the SSHOC task 5.5 enabled an increase in the use of standards and CVs.

2.1.4 Cloud storage

Prior to, and in parallel to the work on task 5.5, a process to move all NSD data holdings and workspaces to the cloud was ongoing. The choice of data cloud storage was thus made at NSD level.

⁶ The [DASISH project](#) [25/01/2022] was funded by the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 283646, and the [SERISS project](#) [25/01/2022] from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 6542221.

2.1.5 Data deposit

In parallel to task 5.5, ESS data is as from October 2021 deposited and uploaded to the new ESS repository through the data deposit tool integrated into the myESS survey management portal (internal ESS tool). This is an adaptation to the work done in task 5.5, rather than part of it.

2.1.6 Data processing programmes

In parallel with task 5.5 implementation, processing of deposited data has been moved to the cloud, and SAS, Stata and SPSS have been replaced by Jupyter Notebook and Python. This allows the processing programs to directly access the metadata stored in Colectica, as well as data files stored in Azure storage. Since the programs can dynamically access metadata, they can be written in a generic form which checks that deposited data files comply with the specified metadata. The same program can then be used with different studies. In addition, the programs do not need to be manually updated when there are changes in the metadata.

2.1.7 ESS website

In parallel to the task 5.5 development work, a new ESS website is being procured in 2022 as part of ESS ERIC's work programme. The CMS of the existing ESS website europeansocialsurvey.org is ageing and the new infrastructure is thus made available from an interim solution at NSD's website via the ESS website until late 2022.

2.1.8 Licences

In December 2020, the ESS website was upgraded with a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 data licence for ESS data, and a CC BY-SA 4.0 licence for ESS metadata/documentation⁷.

2.2 Choices taken during the task 5.5 implementation

2.2.1 Choice of metadata repository (Colectica)

From NSDs experience with development and maintenance of Nesstar, a worldwide "reference implementation" for DDI Codebook, the costs of developing production ready software were known. Developing a new component with functionality equivalent to that of Colectica, and with DDI Lifecycle support on the import, export, and collaborative editing fronts, would have been costly. Hence, it was a sensible choice to extend the collaboration with the Colectica team and commission them to develop

⁷ https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/data/conditions_of_use.html [25/01/2022]

support for controlled vocabularies, elastic search indexing, installation, and maintenance of Colectica repositories in the cloud, among other elements. Purchasing Colectica licences instead of developing an equivalent tool thus freed up large resources and enabled the team to focus on developing a mature and powerful system (in which Colectica is one of many ingredients).

2.2.2 A system of collaborative services

The new ESS service portfolio consists of services that NSD has built, customised services and proprietary services. Open as well as proprietary operating systems (Linux distributions and Windows) are part of the system. Currently, 6 different programming languages are used. Both open (PostgreSQL) and proprietary (Datomic) database technologies are used.

2.2.3 A strong and versatile ESS platform

The primary focus has been to develop a system that combines the value of ESS data with the potential of EOSC and the more general and emerging FAIR ecosystems. To NSD, the work is more of an industrial/engineering challenge mixed with data curation expertise than building a standalone proof-of-concept tool (which has been typical output of many EU-funded projects historically). The output is an EOSC- and production-ready ESS platform, designed to be compatible with national and European/international services and standards, and designed to be interoperable and sustainable. The aim is that the platform will outlive all its current ingredients/implementation details by generations. In the big picture, the Colectica ingredient (as well as other open and proprietary ingredients) should be regarded as an implementation detail.

2.2.4 From data lake to storage in files

A file-based approach to data management has been chosen over a data lake solution, because:

- 1: Statistical files can be processed using statistical libraries, for example for transformations, quality assurance checks and set operations,
- 2: Data file management is less resource intensive when it comes to technology, maintenance and development, as well as more portable and flexible in an ESS context, and
- 3: Data files can be versioned more easily than databases.

Due to the choices (sustainability, use of DDI lifecycle (Colectica), Azure) the achievement in Task 5.5 is at a higher level of development than the pilot status of the project indicates. The one thing that has not been possible within this project was to achieve a higher degree of integration between data and documentation (NSD has opted for a two-repository solution, please refer to Section 2.1). The idea when the project application was sent was to use data lake storage in bases at a granular level. Such a datum-centred approach is supported in the DDI-CDI meta data model (Gregory et al., 2021). Sikt will be

exploring possibilities for funding and implementation of such long-term reliable and efficient data storage technology in the future.

The solution envisioned was to build an integrated on-premises system for metadata curation, data processing and dissemination in which the changes to data at cell level would update metadata automatically and would be version controlled. This was an overly ambitious goal. After re-evaluation of the current technical landscape of NSD (NSDs adoption of GraphQL and the Azure cloud) and the constraints of the project – complexity of the envisioned solution, time, budget, maturity of the DDI-CDI metadata standard, availability of people, the decision of 2020 to adopt Colectica software (repository, designer and workflow), the Azure cloud storage and Azure machine learning (hosts Jupyter notebooks) as components of an overall data archive platform. This has ensured that the goals of the Task 5.5 were achieved within budget and delivery time.

Though Colectica does not support tight integration of metadata with data, systems have been built to ensure integrity of data and its corresponding metadata.

3. Description of repositories and management APIs

3.1 Repositories

The new DDI Lifecycle-based ESS data and metadata repositories have been developed. They are deployed under NSD's tenant in Microsoft Azure. The two-part repository (data and metadata) is integrated with APIs. These APIs link the repositories, the data curators and the data users.

The metadata repository is co-developed with Colectica on their technical platform. By basing the repository for data documentation on an already tried and tested solution and the fruitful cooperation of the company and NSD in developing the Question and Variable Database (QVDB), a workable and sustainable system could be achieved within the available resources. Figure 1 shows the system design of the complete data management system of ESS from data ingestion to data dissemination and how the data and documentation is organised at various stages in the process. The red and grey elements illustrate components that lie out of the scope of the SSHOC Task 5.5. However, as they are important in understanding the structure of the data storage and API solutions developed within the task, they have been included.

Figure 1: System design of the complete data management system of ESS from data ingest to data dissemination

Currently, the metadata repository encompasses ca. 18.000 variables from the 9 ESS rounds that have been conducted so far, and for round 10, which is underway. The variables are structured in 60 data files. It contains metadata at both study and variable levels. Variable information for the ESS main data collections for rounds 1-10 include variable names, labels, formats, values, and value labels as well as hierarchical information on variable concepts and concordance (variable cascade). The repository also includes metadata on the Contact form file (contact data from the fieldwork) and interviewer file (variables on the interviewers and the interviews) for round 10. In addition to documentation at variable level, basic study level information for rounds 1-9 has also been imported into the repository. In ESS, one study (one round of ESS data collection) contains one fieldwork in each participating country. A restructuring of the study level information in Colectica is thus needed to take full advantage of the rich ESS documentation. Data and documentation for each country is therefore organised as individual data collections under each study. The work on structuring and adding further study level documentation will continue/progress in 2022.

The data repository contains published data from all 9 ESS rounds. All published versions are included, except files that are subsets of larger files (for example country files) – a total of around 500 files. The fieldwork for ESS10 is ongoing for the first countries, but it is delayed due to the pandemic. New data is foreseen to be published in September 2022. It will be stored in the new ESS repository and published in autumn/winter 2022. While the data from ESS1-ESS9 has been moved into the cloud storage as processed, integrated files, the ESS10 data delivered in early 2022 will be channelled directly into the processing and storage system in the cloud (shown as the blue and red elements in figure 1). The ESS survey level documentation also encompasses a large amount of Fieldwork documentation; both source material (questionnaires and other materials as developed by ESS ERIC experts) and material translated for use in the participating countries. This includes questionnaires and showcards, information material for ESS respondents, information on interviewer training, sampling and contact between interviewers and respondents. Links to relevant information are included in the metadata repository – at both study and country levels. The files are placed in allocated storage accounts in the ESS cloud storage systems.

3.2 APIs

The APIs are deployed under NSD's tenant in Microsoft Azure. They use a modern API language/interface, GraphQL, to express search and other elements. GraphQL is designed to support strong types and offers flexibility for various clients consuming GraphQL APIs. Moreover, GraphQL APIs encourage decoupling of the externally available API and its types and relations from internal implementation details. Decoupling ensures that API consumers are shielded from internal APIs and systems, offering a stable, flexible, and domain centric API likely to outlive many of its internal technological implementations at any given time. The APIs are standardised on GraphQL since 2018 and they run GraphQL in integration with OAuth2/OpenID connect-based authentication solutions and middleware, supporting fine-grained access control where needed. This means that single sign-on is integrated with the GraphQL API, providing easier access for ESS users. Both the management and dissemination API harvest information directly from the data and metadata repositories.

Furthermore, the API solution allows a workflow where metadata is used for navigation. It provides flexible harvesting of data and metadata that allows data curation through custom requests. This allows the data processing programmes to efficiently access all the relevant metadata from the metadata repository. It also means that any changes or corrections in the metadata will only have to be made in the metadata repository rather than in the data processing programmes. The dissemination APIs will be further discussed in the upcoming deliverable report D5.14, Report on preparing the ESS for Services in the EOOSC, which will describe a set of recommendations, architectures, protocols, and workflows of the ESS services set up as part of the pilot.

3.3 Controlled vocabularies and statistical classifications

NSD has implemented several Controlled Vocabularies in the metadata repository (list in table 1). This, together with the use of controlled vocabularies in the ESS data (values and categories) ensures a high degree of interoperability with other data within the social science domain. The DDI Alliance and CESSDA controlled vocabularies are registered in <https://fairsharing.org/bsg-s001467/>⁸ (Recommendation 8 in S.J.D. Cox et al. 2021).

Table 1. Controlled vocabularies and statistical classifications used in the repositories

CV Name	Publisher	Context used	URL
Keywords	ELSST	Study documentation	https://elsst.CESSDA.eu/
Topic Classification	CESSDA	Study documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/TopicClassification?lang=en
Contributor role	DDI-Alliance	Study documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/ContributorRole?lang=en
Analysis Unit	DDI-Alliance	Study documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/AnalysisUnit?lang=en
Type of instrument	DDI-Alliance	Fieldwork documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/TypeOfInstrument?lang=en
Data source type	DDI-Alliance	Fieldwork documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/DataSourceType?lang=en
Time method	DDI-Alliance	Fieldwork documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/TimeMethod?lang=en
Sampling procedure	DDI-Alliance	Fieldwork documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/SamplingProcedure?lang=en
Date type	DDI-Alliance	Variable documentation	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/DateType?lang=en
ISO 3166-1 country codes	ISO	Study / Variable documentation	https://www.iso.org/
ISO 639-2 language codes	ISO	Variable documentation	https://www.iso.org/
ISCO-08 Occupation codes	ILO	Variable documentation	https://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/isco08/

⁸ <https://fairsharing.org/bsg-s001467/> [25/01/2022]

NACE Rev.2 Industry	EUROSTAT	Variable documentation	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nace-rev2/overview
NUTS Region codes	EUROSTAT	Variable documentation	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/6948381/KS-GQ-14-006-EN-N.pdf
Ancestry codes	ESS	Variable documentation	http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/
Education codes	ESS	Variable documentation	http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/
Religion codes	ESS	Variable documentation	http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/
Marital status	ESS	Variable documentation	http://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/

3.4 Versioning

Good versioning is important to keep track of any changes in data/metadata. ESS will be introducing a new versioning system as of Spring 2022. A plan on how to convey the new system to the ESS user community will be set up alongside its implementation.

3.4.1 Versioning of data and documents

The ESS versioning for data files and documents will be updated from 2 level versioning to a type of semantic versioning. The three levels thus being MAJOR (inclusion of new country data), MINOR (Changes in data or metadata that will influence the use of data or the results of data analysis) and PATCH (insignificant changes such as spelling errors). A new DOI will be minted for changes in MAJOR and MINOR levels. As changes at PATCH level does not influence the results of data analysis or how these are interpreted, a PATCH update will not lead to a new DOI.

3.4.2 Versioning of metadata

ESS metadata elements are versioned at one level only. Every version of an item committed to the repository is saved, allowing clients to retrieve a full version history of any item in the repository. Each version includes additional information such as, for instance, information about the user who committed the version, the date and time the version was committed and an optional message describing the reason for the change (Beuster et al., 2019).

4. FAIR considerations and achievements

After implementation of the development work in Task 5.5, ESS data has improved support for the FAIR principles (Wilkinson, Mark D et al., 2016). This part reports on the FAIR status of ESS data towards the end of the SSHOC project.

The development work aimed to support/implement the following recommendations made in the report Turning FAIR into Reality (TFIR) (the European Commission, 2018).

- Rec. 2: Implement a model for FAIR Digital Objects
 - Action 2.3: Systems must be refined and implemented to make automatic checks on the existence and accessibility of PIDs (Persistent Identifier), metadata, a licence or waiver, and code, and to test the validity of the links between them.
- Rec. 3: Develop components of a FAIR ecosystem
 - Action 3.2: By default, the FAIR ecosystem as a whole and each of its individual components should work for humans and for machines. Policies and DMPs should be machine-readable and actionable.
- Rec. 4: Develop interoperability frameworks for FAIR sharing within disciplines and for interdisciplinary research
 - Action 4.5: The components of the FAIR ecosystem should adhere to common standards to support disciplinary frameworks and to promote interoperability and reuse of data across disciplines.
- Rec. 8: Facilitate automated processing. Automated processing should be supported and facilitated by FAIR components. This means that machines should be able to interact with each other through the system, as well as with other components of the system, at multiple levels and across disciplines.
 - Action 8.2: Metadata standards should be adopted and used consistently to enable machines to discover, assess and utilise data at scale.
 - Action 8.3: Structured discoverability and profile matching mechanisms need to be developed and tested to broker requests and mediate metadata, rights, usage licences and costs.
- Rec. 20: Deposit in Trusted Digital Repositories

- Action 20.3: Concrete steps need to be taken to ensure the development of domain repositories and data services for interdisciplinary research communities, so the needs of all researchers are covered.
- Rec. 23: Develop FAIR components to meet research needs
 - Action 23.1: The development of FAIR-compliant components needs to involve research communities, technical experts, and other stakeholders. They should be provided with a forum for the exchange of views.
 - Action 23.3: FAIR components will need regular iteration cycles and evaluation processes to ensure that they are fit for purpose and meet community needs.

FAIRification is a process that is improved continuously. Therefore, beyond the work within Task 5.5, Sikt aims to continuously improve FAIRification for all data holdings of the agency.

Please note that it has been chosen to detail FAIR achievements using the FAIR principles rather than the TFIR recommendations. As noted by the TFIR report, they chose to take a holistic approach to FAIRification since the notions of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability, and the actions needed to enable them – are deeply intertwined (TFIR p. 10). Therefore, the recommendations are not directly mappable to FAIR principles. However, the task 5.5 team used the above-mentioned recommendations as the guiding vision when making choices on actions related to the individual FAIR principles. The improvements in FAIRness are described below by FAIR principle.

The TFIR report, however, refrains from addressing the FAIR principles and the recommended actions individually, as they are so deeply interwoven. Crosas (2020) provides a good example of a practical FAIR review of an archiving system - Dataverse, which was read with great interest. The source for the below terminology (subheadings and quotes) is <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>⁹ - the clearest guide identified for the exercise.

4.1 Findable

“The first step in (re)using data is to find them. Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Machine-readable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of datasets and services, so this is an essential component of the FAIRification process”.

The new search functionality enables easy search across the data holdings at high-level (series and studies) as well as for details (question text and variables) for users by the end of March 2022. re, and

⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> [25/01/2022]

thus enable even better access to data and metadata. The new landing pages for series, studies and variables are driven by metadata and data within the cloud repositories and use the GraphQL API. The landing pages are also compliant with the current Universal Accessibility standards. APIs are accessible from <https://docs.nsd.no/>¹⁰.

All the metadata relevant to series, rounds and datasets are managed in the Colectica repository based on DDI-LifeCycle metadata standard and are available through graphql API for automated discovery and consumption. Adoption of DDI-Controlled Vocabularies¹¹ for as many DDI-elements as possible makes the metadata highly machine-actionable.

F1: (Metadata are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

DOI has been allocated for published data and metadata at study and data file level. Further, a well-defined versioning regime facilitates management of changes in data and metadata. This will support improvement of the versioning of the DOIs. Preparations are also made for allocation of DOIs at data file level. The ESS DOI in standard Data Citation¹² is compliant with the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles¹³.

Allocation of persistent mechanisms, such as download GraphQL query with references to DOI for downloaded data-subsets enables sharing and referencing over time without being impacted by the newer versions of data and metadata.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

ESS Data is documented using DDI-Lifecycle, an open standard for documenting various stages in the research data lifecycle, such as conceptualization, collection, processing, distribution, discovery, and archiving (<https://ddialliance.org/>). Specified in XML, DDI facilitates reuse of metadata components across the data lifecycle. The most reusable metadata components in the ESS metadata are organisations, concepts, controlled vocabularies and code lists. These elements belong to DDI-schemes and are maintained in so-called resource packages. From here they can be referenced across the ESS rounds by various metadata elements such as ESS datasets, variables, data collection and study level information.

This metadata is stored in the designated Colectica developed metadata repository. A GraphQL API built over the existing Colectica REST API enables faster and easier access to metadata by modern web applications. The data analysis and visualisation in the new ESS metadata landing pages are driven by

¹⁰ <https://docs.nsd.no/> [25/01/2022]

¹¹ <https://ddialliance.org/controlled-vocabularies> [25/01/2022]

¹² [Conditions of Use | European Social Survey \(ESS\). Please note that, for example, doi:10.21338/NSD-ESS9-2018 is the doi reference for data from ESS round 9](#) [25/01/2022]

¹³ <https://www.force11.org/datacitationprinciples> [25/01/2022]

the rich machine-actionable metadata. DDI-XML metadata will be available for download by the end of March 2022.

F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

The metadata explicitly includes an identifier to the actual data file it describes in the DDI-element PhysicalInstance¹⁴. This element is version controlled, for every update to data the version is incremented. This element is available via API and is used to drive data analysis, visualisation, and download.

F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

Elastic search indexing of the metadata will, when it is implemented, expose the ESS data holdings to Google Crawler, making it available through google search. Metadata is registered while minting DOIs at Datacite. Datacite indexes the registered metadata and provides an integrated search interface, where it is possible to search, filter and extract all the details from a collection.

ESS metadata is also harvested by CESSDA and made available through the CESSDA Data Catalogue¹⁵.

4.2 Accessible

"Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorization."

The research community can access ESS data openly. Since the beginning of the ESS in 2002, the principle of free and immediate access to data for all has been an integral part of the design. The ESS data and metadata made available through the system is considered not to be indirectly identifiable. The data has been available without restrictions, for not-for-profit purposes. Only a very simple registration procedure on the ESS website has been needed.

The development work in task 5.5 has added authentication of data users via Google, EduGain/Feide and the ESS user accounts. A login page for ESS-users, listing previous downloads also contributes to easier access.

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol

Jacobsen et al. (2020) hold that implementation of the FAIR principles should enable machines to make optimal use of data resources. According to this source, regarding implementation of Accessible, this means that: "Protocols for retrieving digital resources should be made explicit, for both humans and machines, including well-defined mechanisms to obtain authorization for access to protected data."

¹⁴ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.3/item-types/PhysicalInstance/> [25/01/2022]

¹⁵ <https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/> [25/01/2022]

The current ESS data access system has support for http:// and https:// protocols respectively. The access to data is clearly specified in the metadata and supported by Single Sign On.

A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

- DOI for deaccessioned dataset (data not available) will continue to resolve to metadata landing pages. Hence making them findable and citable though the data analysis and access will not be possible.
- Deaccessioned datasets will be available upon request.
- Metadata will explain clearly and explicitly why the data is not available.

4.3 Interoperable

“The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.”

To allow for integration with other data, the use of stable and mature standards is important. Use of such a standard can mitigate differences in platforms or formats for storing data and metadata, enabling interoperability.

11. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

ESS documents in DDI-Lifecycle 3.3 (DDI-L), a mature domain specific metadata standard. DDI-L is specified in XML format. In addition, a JSON output is available from Colectica. DDI-L also has a rich schema to support extensive variable metadata. Versioning of metadata makes it possible to track the development of items over time. All APIs in the task 5.5 system are based on the use of DDI-L to transfer and interpret the repository content. APIs are accessible from <https://docs.nsd.no/>¹⁶.

12. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

The ESS makes extensive use of controlled vocabularies in data and metadata. CVs are domain-specific and based on CESSDA/DDI maintained vocabularies. See chapter 2.0 for a full list of vocabularies and sources.

13. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Data and metadata within the ESS repository are linked using the DDI element PhysicalInstance¹⁷ and

¹⁶ <https://docs.nsd.no/> [25/01/2022]

¹⁷ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.3/item-types/PhysicalInstance/#physicalinstance> [25/01/2022]

has XML schema¹⁸. Through the PhysicalInstance element, the datafiles are assigned a unique persistent identifier and version number. The physicalInstance is used by machines to access the correct datafiles for visualisation, analysis and download.

4.4 Reusable

“The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimise the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.”

The ESS data is collected not only for a specific study, but with multiple data users in mind. It is thus designed and documented from the planning phases and all through the survey lifecycle. This rich documentation will be made available for researchers, data scientists and survey managers in such a way that not only reuse of data is facilitated. The data with core metadata is available now, further metadata will be made available by the end of March 2022. It is also a goal to allow for reuse of survey and curation methods as well as survey instruments and instrument development.

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

ESS documents data using Colectica and DDI LifeCycle which provides accurate and relevant descriptions of data and metadata.

R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence

This will be described at study level. DDI-L elements “Restrictions”, “Disclaimer” and “Citation Requirement” (under “Archive”) are used. In addition, ESS data access and user terms are described at the following ESS site¹⁹. CC licences²⁰ were added in 2020.

R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

ESS data has:

- Full data citation metadata with credit to data authors, providers, and distributors.
- Versions with changes documented.
- Variables can be linked to the question(s) and instrument from which they origin.
- Clear and explicit licences.

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

The DDI-Lifecycle applied is a relevant domain standard for surveys. The standard, which covers the

¹⁸ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/3.3/XMLSchema/FieldLevelDocumentation/> [25/01/2022]

¹⁹ https://www.europeansocialsurvey.org/data/conditions_of_use.html [25/01/2022]

²⁰ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/> [25/01/2022]

needs of surveys, is increasingly used, and has been recommended to use in the SSHOC project work (Broeder et al., 2019).

4.5 Summary: FAIRness of ESS data and metadata

The FAIRness of ESS data and metadata has improved as follows:

- (1) Adoption of DDI-L for dissemination purposes, in the new ESS service, has facilitated automated processing by analysis, visualisation and download components of the service. This is a concrete example of increased FAIRness of data and implementation of Rec 8, Facilitate automated processing (the European Commission, 2018).
- (2) Adoption of DDI-L for dissemination purposes has powered a smart and powerful search tool. The user can search in the rich metadata and find, for example, the exact variable they are interested in. The findability of data has increased dramatically compared to the earlier ESS service.
- (3) Minting DOI at both study and dataset level supports persistence across versions and helps users understand the changes between versions increasing reusability of data.
- (4) Metadata is available on landing pages for users and through API for machines making it findable to both humans and machines.

There has not been any FAIR scoring exercise undertaken on the new ESS service yet, however, the task 5.5 team is confident that the service will score above average given that, among other things, there are DOIs at study and dataset level, the DDI-L metadata standard is applied, the extensive metadata is available through API and access conditions are defined clearly in the relevant DDI-L metadata elements.

5. Recommendations for a FAIR compliant integrated data and metadata repository

The below list of recommendations is based on NSD's/Sikt's practical implementation of FAIR principles in the updated ESS infrastructure for data storage, management, and distribution.

- (1) Controlled vocabularies/standards should be used where possible. At least, use of domain specific CVs should be applied, but, if possible, use cross-domain CVs/standards, as CVs help increase machine actionability.
- (2) Standardised licence for data and metadata should be set up. The use of standardised licence such as Creative Commons gives data access and is often used as a provenance indicator in the FAIR measurement matrixes thus reassuring researchers in their use and reuse of data.
- (3) Persistent identifiers should be allocated to the own resources to ensure persistence and trackability of changes in data and metadata.
- (4) Cloud storage should be Implemented for the data. This increases the scalability, stability and sustainability of your data storage, and helps secure modern functionality.
- (5) Thorough assessment of the data and metadata organisation in repository (-ies) should be made. This should include the implementation of a stable domain specific metadata standard. ESS ERIC chose the DDI LifeCycle standard, which ensures interoperability and reusability of metadata and data.
- (6) “Off-shelf” opportunities should be explored i.e what can be acquired elsewhere - for example Colectica. For NSD, use of Colectica ensured a time and resource efficient development process.
- (7) The use of APIs should be implemented as it is the contemporary way of accessing various data.
- (8) Landing pages should be user friendly with good user interface design.
- (9) Authentication, access control and user statistics are key elements in data dissemination. Use of single sign-on gives a better user experience and reduces double registration, thus facilitating better user management.
- (10) An archive should be certified, for example with CoreTrustSeal²¹ certification for data archives – as certification improves the trust in the archive’s data holdings among users and publishers (Sikt/ESS ERIC will be applying for CoreTrustSeal certification for the ESS Archive in February 2022).

²¹ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements,
<https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/requirements/> [25/01/2022]

6. Conclusion: lessons learned and next steps

It is hoped that the work undertaken and the improved access to existing data will benefit researchers in and beyond the Social Sciences and Humanities and contribute to the efficiency and productivity of researchers and other types of users.

The development project proved to be demanding technically, including complex infrastructure architecture and innovative use of the Colectica software system. The scope of the project has not allowed time and resources for extensive testing. The hope is that the technical achievements can be examined and tested by users and other organisations.

Two instances of the Colectica repository, processing and publishing, were installed in the Azure cloud. The Colectica workflow service manages publishing of metadata from processing to published repository. The Colectica technical service was commissioned to install, set up and manage the repositories and integrate them with Azure Active Directory. Migration of metadata to Colectica repositories from the on-premises Colectica repository was a straightforward activity. Data was migrated from Nesstar files to Azure storage in SPSS file format. The ESS service API is an extension of NSDs existing graphql API and hence uses the existing infrastructure and architecture. This made it easier to build and maintain the ESS service API.

Rather than being fully "generic", the new services are influenced by NSD's/Sikt's IT topology, authentication regime, skill sets, standardisation policies and architecture decisions. The service is an integrated part of Sikt's data archive platform rather than a standalone solution, and hence, cannot be reused or installed at other locations. However, the metadata and data can be accessed via API and reused by other services.

Overall patterns and overall system designs, workflows and API-policies are likely to be of higher value than the code itself as output. These patterns and designs can be adopted far easier in other organisations than the components can (given technical and architectural heterogeneities between institutions).

The code still has value. NSD/Sikt will share API code and the source code for the services developed by NSD upon request. This will (in theory) enable others to reuse some of the code, and then decide whether they will purchase a Colectica Designer/Repository licence or develop an equivalent component to power the metadata import/curation/export.

For Sikt, areas of probable future investigation include further integration of data and metadata through application of the DDI-CDI metadata model. For a big survey like the ESS, this would have the potential of reducing the workload with minor and larger data upgrades and to give cost savings. Such undertakings, however, demand further funding.

During the last months of and beyond the SSHOC project, efforts will be made to raise awareness about the new data platform through various approaches. ESS ERIC has registered as a service provider in the EOSC portal, and the new data resource “[ESS as a service](#)” is onboarded and available from the EOSC²².

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